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A Comparative Study of Investment Behavior of Retail Investors in Türkiye and Pakistan

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Abstract

The purpose of this study is to investigate and compare the investment behavior of retail investors in Türkiye and Pakistan with an online survey data. Independent sample *t*-test is used to investigate the difference of Financial Literacy, Investors' Confidence, Risk Tolerance, Investment Philosophy, and Investment Experience and Investment choices across countries. The findings show that there are some key differences in the behavior of retail investors in Türkiye and Pakistan. Furthermore, Path Analysis reveals that all five variables under the study i.e., Financial Literacy, Risk tolerance, Investment Philosophy, Experience and Self Confidence proved to be good predictors of Investment Choices in both countries. The study is among the pioneer ones as very scanty literature is available on collective relationship of Financial Literacy, Investors' Confidence, Risk Tolerance, Investment Philosophy, and Investment Experience on Investment choices and how their combined effect reflects on investment behavior.

Keywords: Investment behavior; investment choices; financial literacy; investment philosophy; path analysis.

Introduction

The impact of different factors on investment behavior has received close attention from researchers, consultants, personal financial planners, and investors especially in the last few decades. An individual's behavior and psychological factors like beliefs, preferences, and psychological biases play a vital role in financial decision making (Lodhi, 2014; Mitroi, 2014). Every investor is different, with different financial goals, different levels of risk tolerance, personal situations, and different desires. Investors' personality plays an important role in choosing specific investment tools (Aren & Dinç, 2015). Certain investors show similar behavior due to similarities in socio-economic conditions and psychological factors while other groups of investors may react differently because of those factors. These differences may occur at the regional level as well. There is a need to identify those factors that can help stakeholders, i.e., government, regulatory institutions, banks, investment companies, etc. to develop a deep understanding of certain investment behaviors to tailor their ways of conducting business and executing regulations in a more effective manner. Such factors therefore can also facilitate retail investors to diversify their portfolios and make investment decisions more easily and efficiently. Thus,

understanding the behavior of (retail) investors is critical determining factors that may affect their decision-making process (East, 1993).

The purpose of this study is to identify such determinants while particularly focusing on the attitude of investors towards risk, the role of demographics, and the inner confidence of investors, which may shape investors' personality. Although many studies had been conducted on investment behavior, the studies which explore the collective relationship of factors shaping investment strategy and how these factors are reflected in investment behavior are limited in numbers. In these studies, most of the work revolves around a single country, using a particular survey instrument covering one or two variables at a time (Nicolini et al., 2013). In developing countries like Pakistan, the combined effect of these variables is yet to be found (Awais et al., 2016). It is therefore desirable to understand whether the behavior of investors in one country could be generalized to other regions. As claimed by Nicolini et al. (2013), a unique national environment may compel researchers to study investment behavior in each country individually. Considering this, it is much needed to check the perception differences of investors among countries to get a comparable measurement criterion. Therefore, this study attempts to get an insight into retail investors' behavior in two different countries i.e., Pakistan and Türkiye. The factors which may influence investment behavior include financial capability related to financial knowledge (Atkinson et al., 2010; Gallery, Newton, and Palm 2011; Reddy, R. et al., 2013; Xiao et al., 2015) financial experience (Pellinen et al. 2011; Hani, Heru, and Isworo 2020); investor personality reflecting money/ investment attitude (Pak and Mahmood 2015; Nandan and Kumar 2016) and risk attitude (Septi, Ainia, and Lutfi 2019; Shadnan 2016) as well as demographic variables (Shaikh 2019; Thanki and Baser 2019; Kumar and Goyal 2016) . Understanding the behavior of (retail) investors is critical to determine factors that may affect investment intentions. This study aims to investigate similarities and differences in terms of investment behavior of investors of Pakistan and Türkiye.

Theoretical Background

The factors which may influence investment behavior include financial literacy, experience, investment philosophy/goals, risk tolerance and self-confidence.

Financial Literacy (FL)

Devastating financial crises has increased the importance of financial literacy (Vitt et al., 2005). To measure Financial Literacy, we use the overall literacy score calculated by combining individual scores of 10 items extracted from Houts and Knoll's financial literacy scale developed in 2019 (Houts & Knoll, 2020). Financial literacy does not only help to evaluate different investment choices but gives a logical basis to investors to curve investors' philosophy according to his/her desires. Financial understanding thus leads to establish logical expectations about investment returns (Zait and Berteau 2015). Relationship between Financial literacy and financial experience is also found in literature. A Positive relationship between financial experience and financial literacy was observed. Therefore, the following hypothesis is specified.

H₁: Financial Literacy influences the relationship of Investor's Experience.

Experience (EX)

Investment experience is a psychological factor that influences present decisions of investors in the light of the results obtained in the past (Mak & Ip, 2017a). Experience was measured based on years of experience in investment and the variety of investments instruments in literatür (Frijns et al., 2014). In this study, a 2-questions developed by Nanda and Moa'mer (2013) and 13 items developed by Grable and Lytton (1999) was used. When it comes to investment decisions, experience plays a mixed role. Experienced and inexperienced investors may behave differently in different situations. Therefore, the following hypotheses are framed.

H₂: Experience influences the Risk Tolerance.

H₃: Experience influences the Investment Philosophy.

H₄: Experience influences the Self-Confidence.

Risk Tolerance (RT)

Risk tolerance is defined as "the emotional and psychological components that affect an individual's perception and reaction to risk" (Linciano & Soccorso, 2013). In this study, Self-Assessment Question 01 (Marinellie et. al. in 2017) was used to measure the risk tolerance of individuals. Risk tolerance items were 13 and score is calculated by combining all individuals item scores on the basis of risk tolerance i.e., lower score is given to risk avoiding situations whereas options indicating higher risky possibilities

received maximum score. Risk tolerance plays a significant role in shaping investment intentions (Cuong and Jian 2014). Considering that risk tolerance may affect investment philosophy and investment choices, the following hypotheses are established.

H₅: Risk Tolerance affects the Investment Philosophy

H₆: Risk Tolerance affects the Investment Choices.

Investment Philosophy (IP)

According to Damodaran, an investment philosophy can be defined as a coherent way of thinking about markets, how they work and the types of mistakes that may trigger investor behavior, while investment strategy is a way of an investment philosophy putting into practice (Damodaran, 2007). Regarding investment choices, several options from the literature were selected (Aren & Dinç, 2015; Geetha & Ramesh, 2011; Morse, 1998). Investment choices were given scores based on preferences selection e.g., respondents were asked to select the given investment choices based on their highly preferred choice. 1st preferred choice was given 100 percent weightage, second preferred choice was given 2/3 weightage and 3rd preference was given 1/3rd weightage. Then these scores were combined to calculate final scores of investment choices variable. Considering that Investment Philosophy will affect Investment Choices, the following hypothesis is assumed.

H₇: Investment Philosophy affects the Investment Choices.

Self-Confidence (SC)

Self-confidence is defined as a state of mind in which an individual over rates his/her abilities to perform well in an increasingly challenging environment. Self-confidence about investors' own abilities was assessed by using a 5-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree) (Asaad 2015; Khan, Shah and Bangesh, 2019). Overconfidence influences investment decisions (Nada, 2013). An overconfident person may develop an excessive belief in his/her decision-making skills by ignoring the conditions that could cause adverse impact on outcomes in contrast to what he/she is expecting and novice investors are over-enthusiastic when assessing their abilities to invest in the market (Kusnandar et al., 2019). Confidence may lead to proactive financial decisions (i.e., investor use credit card more frequently) while overconfidence not only distracts the investor's decision-making ability but also influences behavior in a negative

way (Atlas et al. (2019). Considering that Self Confidence will affect Investment Choices, the following hypothesis is formulated.

H₈: Self-Confidence affects the Investment Choices.

Methodology

Target Population and Sample

The sample is comprised of citizens aged above 18 years and purposive sampling method is used. The target population of this study is retail investors of Turkey and Pakistan with some basic financial knowledge or investment experience in a variety of products including stocks/shares, foreign currency, mutual funds, term deposits, insurance etc.

The research relies on the primary data gathered through a structured questionnaire conducted online in October 2020-April 2021 through a private research firm in Pakistan and in Turkey.

As the study is analyzing investment choices as the dependent variable, expert opinions, central bank surveys and investments banks financial reports are used to get the information about the variety of investment choices. A structured questionnaire was developed after reviewing the related literature and several rounds of online discussions with 3 professors, 2 personals working on top positions in Nokia Pakistan. The first part of the questionnaire consists of demographic information and in the second part, there are likert type questions covering 7 structures created by combining different scales. The 43 Item questionnaire along with all the coding and explanations is attached in Appendix 1.

A pilot study of 75 respondents was conducted to check the accuracy of the scale. In the pilot study, the Cronbach's alpha value was examined and it was observed that this value was within acceptable limits with 0.628. (G. Pontekotto and E. Ruckdeschel 2007; Hays, Hayashi, and Stewart 1989; Khidzir, Ismail, and Abdullah 2018; Ursachi, Horodnic, and Zait 2015). Then, the questionnaire was finalized.

Survey Study

Data for the study was collected through an online survey both from Pakistan and Türkiye. After the approval of the questionnaire by the Ethics Committee of Anadolu University. Complete 592 responses were collected. From Pakistan 364 responses were gathered, however after filtering the data, complete responses were reduced to 343. From Türkiye, out of 260 responses 249 complete responses were analyzed. Usually a sample

size > 300 or respondents to item ratio 10:1, is considered enough (Konstantina Vasileiou et al., 2018; Lenth, 2001; Osborne & Costello, 2004; Yurdugül, 2008). Hence, the sample size is adequate for data analysis.

The purpose of the present study was to investigate the pathways by which variables affect investment behavior of retail investors in both countries. Thus, structural path model was used to analyze the paths for linear relationship between the main variables under study. Before proceeding to the path analysis, normality and multicollinearity were investigated.

Path analysis assumes that the residuals of the variables are normally distributed. For large samples i.e. $n > 300$, normality assumption is met when the absolute skewness and kurtosis values are between +2 and +7 (R. Mishra et al., 2019). In this study, all values of Skewness and Kurtosis are in the normality range.

VIF is used to check multicollinearity. The cut-off point is 5, but the values close to 3 or lower than 5 are preferable (Srinivasan & Lohith, 2017). In this study VIF values are smaller than 3. Thus, there is no problem of multicollinearity, which is one of the most important assumptions of path analysis. Descriptive statistics are given in Table 1 and 2.

Questionnaire Reliability

To assess the internal consistency of the items in questionnaire, Cronbach Alpha Coefficient (α) is considered as a good reliability measure. In psychology and social sciences, the values $>.6$ is acceptable (G. Pontekotto and E. Ruckdeschel 2007). However, the value of α also depends on the number of items in a construct (Ercan et al., 2007; Javali et al., 2011). Alpha is most frequently used, but it is not the most accurate reliability coefficient (Brunner & Süß, 2005; Cho, 2016). So composite reliability (CR.) is also calculated.

A composite reliability score is also used to check inter relationship of observed items. It is calculated by dividing the number of items (n) to sum of squared loadings of items. The value ranges from 0 to 1. The desirable values are between .7 to .9, however a value above .6 is acceptable (Ab Hamid et al., 2017). For inter item correlation, values between .15 to .50 are acceptable, (Clark and Watson 2015, p. 176). In cross cultural studies, an issue of non-equivalence is also observed. There are some items that are

adequate for one country, but not performing well in other country although the overall performance of the whole data is good (Byrne & van de Vijver, 2010). Table 3 shows Cronbach alpha, CR., and inter-item correlation values.

Hypothesis

The hypothesis to be tested with Path Analysis are as follows:

- $H_{o(a1)}$: Financial Literacy influences investment behavior of retail investors in Türkiye and Pakistan.
- $H_{o(a2)}$: Investment Experience influences investment behavior of retail investors in Türkiye and Pakistan.
- $H_{o(a3)}$: Risk Tolerance influences investment behavior of retail investors in Türkiye and Pakistan.
- $H_{o(a4)}$: Investment Philosophy influences investment behavior of retail investors in Türkiye and Pakistan.
- $H_{o(a5)}$: Self Confidence influences investment behavior of retail investors in Türkiye and Pakistan.

Related to Effect size:

- $H_{o(b1)}$: The effect size of Financial Literacy differs significantly among the retail investors in Türkiye and Pakistan.
- $H_{o(b2)}$: The effect size of Investment Experience differs significantly among the retail investors in Türkiye and Pakistan.
- $H_{o(b3)}$: The effect size of Risk Tolerance differs significantly among the retail investors in Türkiye and Pakistan.
- $H_{o(c4)}$: The effect size of Investment Philosophy differs significantly among the retail investors in Türkiye and Pakistan.
- $H_{o(c4)}$: The effect size of Self- Confidence differs significantly among the retail investors in Türkiye and Pakistan.

Findings

Model Fit Indices

The most widely used model fit indices in path analysis are *GFI*, *NFI*, *TLI*, *CFI*, *IFI*, *RFI*, *CMIN/Df*. The values above .90 are acceptable (Stage et al., 2004). The frequently used two measures *RMSEA* (The root mean square error of approximation) and *SRMR*

(Standardized root mean square residual) provide information about residuals' spread. *RMSEA* assesses "How far the hypothesized model is from the perfect model". *SRMR* is "The difference between the observed correlation and the model implied correlation matrix". *RMSEA* has a cut-off value close to .05 is recommended although a value less than .08 is acceptable. The acceptable range for *SRMR* is between 0 and .08 (Hu & Bentler, 1999). The model fit indices of current path analysis indicated that all the values are in the acceptable range. *GFI* (Goodness of Fit Index) = .971, *NFI* (Normed Fit Index) = .943, *TLI* (Tucker-Liwise Index) = .900. *CFI* (Comparative Fit Index) = .953, *IFI* (Incremental Fit Index) = .954, *RFI* (Relative Fit Index) = .877. $X^2/df = (CMIN/Df) = 4.936$, *RMSEA* = .058 and *SRMR* = .0463. The baseline model met the criteria of adequate fit, as all the values are in the acceptable range (Appendix 4 presents model fit index criteria by Kyndt and Onghena (2014)). The Unstandardized and Standardized weights, Standard errors (*S.E*), Critical Ratio (*CR*), p values and R^2 values of the baseline model are given in Table 4. The standardized weights column has path coefficients (slopes, β) for the regression of Experience on Self- Confidence and Investment Philosophy, Risk Tolerance on Investment Choices and Investment Philosophy, Self- Confidence, and Investment Philosophy on Investment Choices as well as Financial Literacy on Experience. Their Squared Multiple Correlation Coefficient (R^2) are also given. These values describe "the proportion of the variation in the dependent variable explained by the independent variables in the model".

Direct and Indirect Effects

Table 5 presents standardized values for the direct and indirect effects of the baseline model. Financial Literacy has a direct (unmediated) effect on Experience only. In other words, when Financial Literacy goes up by 1 standard deviation, Experience goes up by 0.41 standard deviations. In addition, Financial Literacy has also an indirect effect on Self Confidence. The standardized indirect (mediated) effect of Financial Literacy on Self Confidence is .164. Financial Literacy has also an indirect effect on Risk Tolerance, Self Confidence, and Investment Choices (Effect values are presented in Table 4.2.1). Investment Choices has a direct effect on three variables i.e., the standardized direct effect of Risk Tolerance on Investment Choices is .266, Investment Philosophy is .311 and Self Confidence is .118. This is in addition to the indirect effect Risk Tolerance

(.072), Investment Experience (.318) and Financial Literacy (.131) have on Investment Choices.

Country-wise Comparison

After checking the relationship of the variables of the study in the hypothesized model, the next step is to compare the country-wise models. Models for Türkiye and for Pakistan were developed and analyzed for this purpose. The regression weights (β) of all the variables are significant ($p < .05$) in both models.

The goodness of fit measures for the individual models of retail investors in Türkiye and Pakistan are presented in Table 4.3.1. The model fit was better for Türkiye ($CFI=.961$, $RMSEA=.074$, $CMIN/DF = 2.349$) compared to Pakistan ($CFI= .929$, $RMSEA = .141$, $CMIN/DF = 7.74$). Table 4.3.2 presents the total effect of all variables for both models. The effect of Financial Literacy on Investment Experience of Turkish (5.99 ± 1.76) and Pakistani Investors (6.44 ± 2.33) is almost the same (41%) at $p < .001$.

Due to relatively lower goodness of fit values for Pakistan, Turkish Model seems to explain influence of other variables on Investment Choices better than Pakistani Model. For Türkiye (as seen in Table 4.3.3), R^2 value is .115, which implies that the predictor variables are accounted for approximately 11.5% of the variation in Investment Choices variable. For Pakistan (as seen in Table 4.3.4), R^2 value is .431, which implies that the predictor variables in the model are accounted for almost 43.1% of the variation in Investment Choices variable. The path coefficients (β) are the parameters of the model and represent the estimates of effective connectivity. Path coefficient represents the response of the endogenous variable to a unit change in an exogenous variable when other variables in the model are held constant. The path coefficients in both models are also significantly different for same paths, which indicates that the nature of relationship of variables in two models are different. For example, the total effect of Risk Tolerance on Investment Choices in Turkish model is .234 and in Pakistan it is .492.

Conclusion

Understanding the behavior of retail investors is critical to determine the factors that may affect investment choices.

All the variables investigated under the study i.e., Financial Literacy, Risk Tolerance, Experience, Investment Philosophy and Self Confidence are shown to be good

predictors of the Investment Choices of retail investors in both countries. Yet, there are some differences in investment choices of retail investors in Türkiye and Pakistan due to socio-economic and demographic variations.

To the best of our knowledge, this is the first comparative study about the behavior of Turkish and Pakistani retail investors. The findings of the current study may help financial institutions to identify specific retail segments to customize their products and services according to the needs and demands of their target clients. Yet, the findings of the study are limited to the subjective nature of variables. Thus, generalization of the findings needs to be considered with caution as the potential for results variance exists. The current study also inherits the limitations associated with a survey-based study. A major part of the sample under study comprises of males' investors, so in future, a sample with a good representation of female investors may help to unfold their investment personality and behavior in more meaningful ways. In the current study, only a set of traditional Investment choices were considered. Adding other options like derivatives, digital currency and hybrid investment choices etc. can be suggested for further studies.

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Table 1. Descriptive Statistics of Demographic Variables

Turkey (n1 = 249)										
	Gender	Age			Qualification		Income		Occupation	
Frequency	Male	15	18-	87	< High	3	0-\$350	35	Employer	22
	Female	2	25	15	School	42	\$351-	16	Employee	145
		97	26-	6	High	16	\$1370	7	Self	54
			55	4	School	2	\$1371-	27	Employed	28
			56-	2	University	42	\$2075	16	Student	
			64		MS/PhD		\$2076-	4		
			64+				\$2760			
							\$2760-			
							above			

Pakistan (n2 = 343)										
	Gender	Age			Qualification		Income		Occupation	
Frequency	Male	260	18-	111	< High	2	0-\$350	70	Employer	109
	Female	83	25	171	School	54	\$351-	143	Employee	150
			26-	48	High	179	\$1370	86	Self	72
			55	13	School	108	\$1371-	33	Employed	12
			56-		University		\$2075	11	Student	
			64		MS/PhD		\$2076-			
			64+				\$2760			
							\$2760-			
							above			

Table 2. Descriptive Statistics Of The Main Variables

Statistics	Self Confidence	Risk Tolerance	Financial Literacy	Investment Philosophy	Experience	Investment Choices
Mode	3.60	29.00	8.00	15.00	5.00	14.00

Mean		3.21	28.36	6.26	14.67	4.89	13.64
Std. Deviation		.851	5.56	2.12	3.54	1.80	3.10
Skewness		-.422	.072	-.874	.258	-.012	-.369
Std. Error of Skewness		.100	.100	.100	.100	.100	.100
Kurtosis		-.337	.162	-.049	-.060	-.722	-.595
Std. Error of Kurtosis		.201	.201	.201	.201	.201	.201
VIF		1.226	1.638	1.240	1.624	1.533	1.226
Minimum		1.20	13.00	0.00	6.00	1.00	3.00
Maximum		5.00	44.00	10.00	24.00	8.00	18.00
N	Valid	592	592	592	592	592	592
	Missing	0	0	0	0	0	0
Range	Absolute Skewness				±2		
	Absolute Kurtosis				±7		

Table 3. Cronbach's α , Composite Reliability and Interitem Correlation

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.721	.772	6
Variables	CR: Composite Reliability	Interitem correlation
Self Confidence	.862	.443
Investment Philosophy	.644	.350
Financial Literacy	.605	.294
Risk Tolerance	.755	.225
Experience	.719	.231
Investment Choices	.659	.169
Total	.781	.361

Table 4. The β , S.E, CR, and R^2 values of the Baseline/ Default model

Variables and links		Unstandardized weights	Standardized weights β	S.E.	CR	P
Experience	← Financial Literacy	0.36	0.42	0.03	10.94	***
Risk Tolerance	← Experience	1.52	0.49	0.11	13.33	***
Investment Philosophy	← Experience	0.52	0.27	0.07	6.88	***
Investment Philosophy	← Risk Tolerance	0.26	0.41	0.02	10.98	***
Self-Confidence	← Experience	0.18	0.39	0.02	10.08	***
Investment Choices	← Self-Confidence	0.43	0.12	0.13	3.36	***
Investment Choices	← Investment Philosophy	0.27	0.31	0.04	7.56	***
Investment Choices	← Risk Tolerance	0.15	0.27	0.02	6.51	***
Squared Multiple Correlations: (Full- Default model)					R^2	
Experience					177	
Risk Tolerance					243	
Investment Philosophy					345	
Self Confidence					153	
Investment Choices					296	

Table 5. Effects of the Predictor Variables on Investment Choices

a: Weighted correlations of Main Study Variables for the Total Sample

Standardized Direct Effect	Financial Literacy	Experience	Risk Tolerance	Investment Philosophy	Self Confidence	Investment Choices
Financial Literacy	1					
Experience	.421**	1				
Risk Tolerance	-	0.493**	1			
Investment Philosophy	-	0.267**	0.408**	1		
Self Confidence		0.391**	-	-	1	
Investment Choices	-	-	0.266**	0.311	.118**	1

Note *** $p < .001$

b. Standardized Indirect Effects

Variables	Financial Literacy	Experience	Risk Tolerance	Investment Philosophy	Self Confidence
Experience	-				
Risk Tolerance	.208	-			
Investment Philosophy	.197	.201	-		
Self Confidence	.164	-	-	-	
Investment Choices	.136	.323	.127	-	-

Table 6 Model Fit Comparison between Türkiye and Pakistan

Model Fit Measure	Türkiye	Pakistan
χ^2 Test of Model Fit (df)	16.43 (7)	54.22(7)
P(χ^2)	0.024	0.000
Cmin/df	2.349	7.74
CFI	.961	.929
RMSEA (90% CI)	0.074	0.141
P (RMSEA \leq .05)**	0.17	0.00
SRMR	0.048	0.0767
NFI	0.936	0.928

Table 7. Standardized Total Effects in grouping Models

Variables	Türkiye					Pakistan				
	FL	EX	RT	SC	IP	FL	EX	RT	SC	IP
Experience	0.41	-	-	-	-	0.41	-	-	-	-
Risk Tolerance	0.21	0.50	-	-	-	0.20	0.48	-	-	-
Self Confidence	0.13	0.31	-	-	-	0.18	0.43	-	-	-
Investment Philosophy	0.16	0.39	0.33	-	-	0.22	0.53	0.45	-	-
Investment Choices	0.08	0.20	0.23	0.15	0.14	0.17	0.40	0.49	0.13	0.36

Table 8. Standardized Regression Weights: (Turkiye)

Variables and links		Unstandar dized weights	Standardi zed weights β	<i>S.E.</i>	<i>CR</i>	<i>P</i>
Risk Tolerance	← Experience	1.62	0.50	0.18	9.16	***
Investment Philosophy	← Experience	0.39	0.23	0.11	3.55	***
Investment Philosophy	← Risk Tolerance	0.18	0.33	0.03	5.12	***
Self-Confidence	← Experience	0.17	0.31	0.03	5.18	***
Investment Choices	← Self-Confidence	0.50	0.15	0.20	2.54	0.01
Investment Choices	← Investment Philosophy	0.14	0.14	0.07	2.02	0.04
Investment Choices	← Risk Tolerance	0.11	0.19	0.04	2.82	0.01
Squared Multiple Correlations: (Full- Default model)						<i>R</i> ²

Financial Literacy	.000
Experience	.168
Risk Tolerance	.253
Investment Philosophy	.235
Self Confidence	.098
Investment Choices	.115

Table 9. Standardized Regression Weights: (Pakistan)

Variables and links		Unstandardized weights	Standardized weights β	<i>S.E.</i>	<i>CR</i>	<i>P</i>
Experience	← Financial Literacy	0.34	0.41	0.04	8.41	***
Risk Tolerance	← Experience	1.46	0.48	0.14	10.21	***
Investment Philosophy	← Experience	0.31	0.45	0.03	9.77	***
Investment Philosophy	← Risk Tolerance	0.65	0.31	0.10	6.73	***
Self-Confidence	← Experience	0.16	0.43	0.02	8.84	***
Investment Choices	← Self-Confidence	0.28	0.36	0.04	6.87	***
Investment Choices	← Investment Philosophy	0.18	0.33	0.03	6.44	***
Investment Choices	← Risk Tolerance	0.56	125.00	0.19	2.96	0.00
Squared Multiple Correlations: (Full- Default model)						R^2
Financial Literacy						.00
Experience						.17
Risk Tolerance						.23
Investment Philosophy						.43
Self Confidence						.18

Figure 1a. Path Analysis of Investors' behavior (Türkiye)

Figure 1b. Path Analysis of Investors' behavior (Pakistan)